

Supporting Information

Two distinct bacterial biofilm components trigger metamorphosis in the colonial hydrozoan *Hydractinia echinata*

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1. General Procedures

NMR measurements were performed on a Bruker AVANCE III 500 MHz and 600 MHz spectrometer, equipped with a Bruker Cryoplatfom. The chemical shifts are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to the solvent residual peak of MeOD-*d*₄ (¹H: 3.31 ppm, quintet; ¹³C: 49.00 ppm, heptet) and D₂O (¹H: 4.79 ppm). **UHPLC-HESI-HRMS** measurement was performed on a Dionex Ultimate3000 system combined with a Q-Exactive Plus mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) with a heated electrospray ion source (HESI). Metabolite separation was carried out using a Luna Omega C18 column (100 x 2.1 mm, particle size 1.6 μm, pore diameter 100 Å, Phenomenex) preceded by a SecurityGuard™ ULTRA guard cartridge (2 x 2.1 mm, Phenomenex). Column oven was set to 40 °C. Metabolite separation was followed by a data-dependent MS/MS analysis in both negative (MS¹) and positive (MS¹ and MS²) ionization modes. The gas flow rates were set to 35 and 10 for the sheath and auxiliary gases, respectively. The capillary and the probe heater temperatures were 340 °C and 200 °C, respectively. The spray voltages were 4 kV and 3.3 kV for the positive and negative ionization modes, respectively. S-lens RF level was set to 50. MS¹ had the resolving power set to 70,000 FWHM at *m/z* 200, scan range to *m/z* 150 – 2,000; injection time to 100 ms; and AGC to 3e6. The ten most intense ions were selected for MS² with a scan rate of 12 Hz. Resolving power was 17,500 FWHM at *m/z* 200, AGC target was 1e5, and injection time was 50 ms. Fragmentations were performed at 28 NCE (normalized collision energy). Data analysis was performed with Thermo XCalibur software (Thermo Scientific). **UHPLC-MS measurements** were performed on a Shimadzu LCMS-2020 system equipped with single quadrupole mass spectrometer using a Phenomenex Kinetex C18 column (50 x 2.1 mm, particle size 1.7 μm, pore diameter 100 Å). Column oven was set to 40 °C; scan range of MS was set to *m/z* 150 to 2,000 with a scan speed of 10,000 u/s and event time of 0.25 s under positive and negative mode. DL temperature was set to 250 °C with an interface temperature of 350 °C and a heat block of 400 °C. The nebulizing gas flow was set to 1.5 L/min and dry gas flow to 15 L/min. **Semi-preparative HPLC** was performed on a Shimadzu HPLC system using a Phenomenex Synergi HydroRP C18 250 x 10 mm column (particle size 5 μm, pore diameter 100 Å). Size exclusion based semipreparative HPLC was performed on a Shodex Asahipak GF-310HQ 300 x 7.5 mm column (particle size 5 μm, pore diameter 400 Å). **Solid phase extraction** was carried out using Chromabond SiOH cartridges filled with 2 g and 10 g of silica gel (Macherey-Nagel, Germany). **Open column chromatography** was performed on Sephadex LH20 (GE Healthcare, Sweden) and G25 (Sigma-Aldrich). **Chemicals:** Methanol (VWR, Germany); water for analytical and preparative HPLC (Millipore, Germany); formic acid (Carl Roth, Germany); acetonitrile (VWR as LC-MS grade); media ingredients (Carl Roth, Germany), marine broth (MB, Carl Roth, Germany); standard phospholipids were ordered from Avanti Polar Lipid.

2. General Procedures for Assessment of *Hydractinia* Morphogenesis

Isolation of *H. echinata* surface-associated bacteria: Six freshly collected gastropod shells were used to dissect 20 *Hydractinia* polyps per shell. Polyps were rinsed with sterile seawater, and crushed in phosphate buffered saline (100 μ L). For the isolation of bacteria, tissue samples were serially diluted from 10^{-1} – 10^{-3} with filtered sterile seawater and 100 μ L of the dilutions were inoculated on marine agar plates (e.g. marine broth (MB), sea water complete medium (SWC) or R2A medium) supplemented with 0.05 mg/L cycloheximide. Plates were incubated at 20 °C for up to 14 days and monitored every day. Colonies showing different morphology were transferred to new agar plates several times until pure cultures were obtained. Bacterial isolates were cultured in liquid MB and SWC media respectively (30 °C for 1–3 days) and maintained as 25% (v/v) glycerol suspensions at -80 °C.

Figure S1. A) *Hydractinia echinata* colonizing the shell inhabited by a hermit crab (*Pagurus* sp.). B-F) Microscopic image of A) fertilized eggs, C) competent planula larva; D) initiation of morphogenic transformation by body shrinking, E) disc formation (settlement); F) formation of primary polyp (metamorphosis).

Bioassay: In general 20-30 competent larvae in sterile-filtered artificial sea water (ASW) were added to each test well and filled up by ASW to reach 2 mL. For all experiments and if not otherwise mentioned: sterile ASW and PBS were used as negative controls and CsCl solution (6 mM final concentration) as positive control.^[1] Experiments were performed as triplicate of 2-3 different larvae batches obtained from different spawning events. The results are indicated as mean value of replicates.

General Assay Procedure (GAP) for colony-based assay (GAP 1): Bacterial strains were grown on a MBA plate for three days. For colony assays, a colony was suspended in 100 μ L PBS (OD_{600} of 0.2) and transferred to 24-well plates. The suspension was incubated for 20 min at r.t. to allow bacterial surface attachment. Then, approximately 20–30 competent larvae of *H. echinata* were added to each well and kept at 20 °C for 48 h to evaluate the percentage of settlement and metamorphosis

Dose response curve of P1-9A sample (GAP2): 1 g of lyophilized P1-9A sample was dissolved in 5 mL sterile sea water and aliquots (4 – 260 μ g) were added to a 24 well plate. Then, 20-30 competent larvae were added per well

and each well was filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The 24-well plates were stored in the dark at 20 °C (**Figure S3**).

Testing of chemically and physically treated cell pellet samples (P1-9P and P1-9A) and chemical extracts (GAP3): Treated samples were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 10 min at 4 °C resulting in an insoluble pellet (“pellet”) and supernatant (“sup”). For assays, the pellet was suspended in 1 mL sterile sea water and supernatant was used without further dilution. Of each sample (sup or cell pellet) 60 µL were added to a sterile 24-well and dried under sterile laminar. 20-30 competent larvae were added and finally filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The 24-well plates were placed in the dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h (**Figure S3, Figure S5, Figure S6, Figure S7, Figure S8, Figure S10**).

Testing of metabolite extracts: Marine Bacteria were grown in 100 mL MB medium at 30 °C for 3 days (160 rpm), other bacteria were grown in LB medium at 30 °C for 3 days (160 rpm). Supernatant was separated from cultures by centrifugation and loaded on an activated SPE-C18 cartridge (500 mg) and eluted with 50% MeOH and 100% MeOH, respectively. The eluted fractions were dried under reduced pressure, and resuspended to concentrations of 1 mg/mL in 50% MeOH or 100% MeOH, respectively, and used for bioassays.

Standard lipids assay (GAP4): Each commercial phospholipid was dissolved in MeOH to give a 1 mg/mL stock solution. For assays, 50 or 25 µM (50 or 25 nmol/mL) were applied per well as final concentration and dried under sterile laminar. Then, 20-30 competent larvae were added and finally filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The 24-well plates were placed in the dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h.

Dose-response curve of commercial phospholipid 16:0 lyso PE (GAP9): Phospholipid 16:0 lyso PE was dissolved in 100 % MeOH to give a 1 mg/mL stock solution. For assays 200 µL, 100 µL, 50 µL, 25 µL and 12.5 µL of the stock solution were added per well, dried under sterile laminar flow and 20-30 competent larvae were added per well. Each well was filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total and the 24-well plates were placed in the dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h (**Figure S14**).

Dose-response curve of Rha-Man (GAP5): Polysaccharide Rha-Man was dissolved in H₂O to give a 10 mg/mL stock solution. For assays, 40, 20, 10 or 2 µL of the stock solution were added per well, dried under sterile laminar flow and 20-30 competent larvae were added per well. Each well was filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total and the 24-well plates were placed in the dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h (**Figure S17**).

Commercial polysaccharides assay (GAP6): Commercial polysaccharide was dissolved into deionized H₂O to give a 1.0 mg/mL stock solution and sterilized by membrane filtration (0.22 µm). Insoluble polysaccharide, eg. curdlan and paramylon, were autoclaved at 120 °C for 10 min. For assays, 100 µL or 50 µL of each stock solution were applied per well and dried under sterile laminar flow. Then, 20-30 competent larvae were added to each well and filled up with sterile sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The 24-well plates were placed in the dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h.

Testing of phospholipid combinations (GAP7): Based on preliminary experiments, seven commercial lipids were selected for combination assays and all possible 1:1 combination thereof were tested. Lipids were dissolved into MeOH to give a 1 mg/mL stock solution, and 50 or 25 µM of the respective lipids were added per well, mixed thoroughly, and dried under sterile laminar flow. As control, each lipid was tested alone. 20-30 competent larvae were added per well and each well was filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The 24-well plates were stored in dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h.

Combination of phospholipid and curdlan (GAP8): Seven phospholipids (MeOH: 1 mg/mL stock solution) were selected for combination assays with the bacterial polysaccharide Rha-Man, which was dissolved in sterile ddH₂O to give a 1 mg/mL stock solution. Per well, 15 µg/mL of curdlan and 10 µg/mL of each lipid was added. Samples were

mixed thoroughly, and dried using sterile laminar flow. Then, 20-30 competent larvae were added per well and the well filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. As a control, curdlan (15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and each lipid was tested alone (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The 24-well plates were placed in dark at 20 °C and evaluated after 24 and 48 h.

3. Chemical Analysis of Morphogens

P1-9 EPS preparation: P1-9 biofilm was grown in 6-well plate filled up with 10 mL MBL for 3 d at 30 °C. The developed biofilm was collected and transferred to a sterile centrifuge tube. After adding the same volume of PBS, 2 g of fine glass beads were added and vortexed for 1 min. After short centrifugation, the supernatant was transferred to fresh tubes and 0.2 M NaOH was added to a final concentration of 0.1 M NaOH. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 10 min with short periodic vortexing after 5 min and in the end of incubation. To neutralize the sample, it was cooled on ice for 5 min, then cold 0.4 M HCl was added to a final concentration of 0.1 M (pH to 7). The supernatant was separated by centrifugation at 10000g for 10 min at 4 °C, and then transferred into fresh Falcon tube, and 3-fold volume of cold 96% EtOH was added. The solution was left at 4 °C for 20 h to precipitate the EPS. After centrifugation (10000 g, 10 min, 4 °C) the supernatant was discarded and the pellet was dried overnight at 55 °C oven. The precipitated EPS was re-dissolved in deionized water (5 mL of 0.5% NaCl), and re-precipitated by adding 3-fold volume of cold 96% EtOH at 4 °C for 20 h. The precipitated EPS was collected by centrifugation at 10000 g for 10 min at 4 °C, and supernatant was discarded. EPS was dried at 55 °C oven for overnight, re-dissolved in 1 mL sterile H₂O and 30 µL were used for bioassays (modified after Dogsa et al., 2013).²

Isolation of outer membrane vesicles: Cells of a 500 mL P1-9 culture in MBL were harvested by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 20 min, r.t.). The cell pellet was washed three times with 1 mL sterile PBS and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min (r.t.). The supernatant was suspended in 30 mM N-octyl-3-D-glucopyranoside (OGP) and centrifuged at 100.000 g for 1 h at 4 °C. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was suspended in 50 µL 30 mM n-octyl-β-D-glucopyranoside (OGP, Carl Roth). Testing of minicell, outer double track layer fractions:³ 20 µL of the corresponding sample was added to a sterile 24-well and evaporated to dryness under sterile laminar for one hour. (**Figure S4**). Activity of OGP was tested separately.

Cell pellet preparation: P1-9 (500 mL, MBL) was incubated at 30 °C for three days (150 rpm). Then, cultures were centrifuged for 20 min at 4 °C (4000 rpm). To remove media components, the resulting cell pellet was washed three times (pellet was suspended in 5 mL sterile PBS, centrifuged (20 min, 4 °C, 4000 rpm) and the supernatant was discarded). The washed cell pellet (sample: **P1-9P**) was suspended in 1 mL sterile water and sonicated on ice (5 x for 30 sec with 30 sec break) to break the cells. To remove soluble cytosolic components, samples were centrifuged (10000 rpm, 10 min, 4 °C), the supernatant discarded and the resulting cell pellet lyophilized overnight (sample: **P1-9A**). For further enzymatic and chemical treatments ca. 600 µg of each obtained extracts (**P1-9P**, **P1-9A**) were suspended in 1 mL sterile water.

DNase treatment: P1-9P and P1-9A samples (1 mL) were treated with 5 mg DNaseI at 37 °C overnight (150 rpm). Afterwards, the enzyme was inactivated by incubation at 90 °C for 5 min and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in 1 mL of sterile water and 60 µL of supernatant and pellet were used for metamorphosis assays according to **GAP2 (Figure S5, Figure S6)**.

RNase treatment: 1 mL of **P1-9P** and **P1-9A** samples were treated with 10 mg RNaseA at r.t. overnight (150 rpm). Afterwards, the enzyme was inactivated by incubation at 90 °C for 5 min and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in 1 mL of sterile water, centrifuged and 60 µL of supernatant and pellet, respectively, were used for metamorphosis assays according to **GAP2 (Figure S5, Figure S6)**.

Proteinase K treatment: 1 mL of **P1-9P** and **P1-9A** samples were treated with 15 mg Proteinase K at 56 °C overnight (150 rpm). The enzyme was inactivated by incubation at 90 °C for 5 min and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in 1 mL of sterile water, centrifuged and 60 µL of supernatant and pellet were used for metamorphosis assays according to **GAP2 (Figure S5, Figure S6)**.

Heating: P1-9P and P1-9A samples were filled up to 1 mL with sterile water and incubated at 30, 56 or 90 °C and 150 rpm overnight (16 h), centrifuged and 60 µL were used for metamorphosis assays according to **GAP2 (Figure S5)**.

P1-9 multiple treatment (P1-9A 3+) and size exclusion ultrafiltration: P1-A samples were suspended in 500 µL sterile water and reacted with 500 µL Proteinase K (15 mg/mL) overnight (16 h) at 37 °C. Then, the suspension was heated for 3 h at 90 °C at 150 rpm. In a second step, HCl was added to a final concentration of 6 M and the suspension incubated overnight (16 h) at 30 °C and 150 rpm. Afterwards, suspension was neutralized with NaOH and concentrated by centrifugation (15000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C) using a Vivaspin 500 PES 100 kDa filter (Sartorius). The retentate was suspended in 1 mL sterile water and 20 µL were used for metamorphosis assay. The flow through was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C using a Vivaspin 500 PES 30 kDa filter (Sartorius). Then, the retentate was suspended in 1 mL sterile water and 20 mL were used for metamorphosis assay. The flow through was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 20 min at 4°C using a Vivaspin 500 PES 5 kDa filter (Sartorius). For testing, the retentate was suspended in 1 mL sterile water and 20 µL of the solution was added to a sterile 24-well and evaporated to dryness under sterile laminar for one hour. The resulting eluent (below 5 kD) was concentrated down and solubilized in 1 mL sterile water and 20 µL of the solution were used for metamorphosis assays (**Figure S8**).

NaOH treatment: P1-9P and P1-9A samples were suspended in 500 µL of 6 M NaOH, sonicated for 15 min at r.t. and incubated overnight at 150 rpm (30 °C). The suspension was neutralized with HCl and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in 1 mL of sterile water, centrifuged and 60 µL of supernatant and pellet used for metamorphosis assays according to **GAP2 (Figure S7)**.

HCl treatment: P1-9P and P1-9A samples were suspended in 500 µL of 6 M HCl, sonicated for 15 min and incubated overnight at 150 rpm (30 °C). The suspension was neutralized with NaOH, and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in 1 mL of sterile water and 60 µL of supernatant and pellet were used for metamorphosis assays (**Figure S5, Figure S6 and Figure S5**).

H₂O treatment: P1-9P and P1-9A samples were suspended in 1 mL sterile water and sonicated for 1 h in a water bath (30 °C) and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min. The pellet was suspended in sterile water to a concentration of 5 mg/mL, and 50 µL of the solution were used for metamorphosis assays (**Figure S8**).

DMSO extraction: P1-9P sample was suspended in DMSO (1 mL with 0.1% TFA) and sonicated for 1 h in a water bath (30 °C) and centrifuged (13,000 rpm, 20 min). The supernatant (sup) was collected, lyophilized and suspended in sterile water to a concentration of 5 mg/mL. The pellet was collected and then suspended in sterile water to a concentration of 5 mg/mL. For metamorphosis assays, 50 µL of each solution was used (**Figure S7**).

Unpolar metabolite extraction (cyclohexane, CHCl₃): P1-9P sample was mixed with 10 mL CHCl₃/MeOH (2:1), sonicated for 5 min in a water bath (30 °C) and then centrifuged (13,000 rpm, 20 min) to remove insoluble material. Then, 10 mL CHCl₃ and 10 mL H₂O were added and the mixture was separated using a separation funnel. The lipid

extract (CHCl₃ or cyclohexane layer) was collected and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. A stock solution with 5 mg/mL in MeOH was prepared for metamorphosis assays.

Other solvent extraction: P1-9P samples were suspended in 10 mL of EtOAc, cyclohexane, CHCl₃, MeOH or sterile water and sonicated for 1 h in an ultrasonication water bath and then kept in the corresponding solvent for 5 h. The suspension was centrifuged (4000 rpm, 20 min) resulting in a supernatant fraction (“sup”) and a pellet (“pellet”). The pellet was dried and re-suspended in 1 mL of the corresponding solvent and 50 μL were used for metamorphosis assays. The supernatant was dried and re-dissolved again in 1 mL of the corresponding solvent of which 50 μL were used for metamorphosis assays (**Figure S10**).

Figure S2. Representative isolation scheme of cell membrane components.

Figure S3. Metamorphosis assay: dose-response curve of P1-9 pellet [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Figure S4. Metamorphosis assays of isolated membrane components of P1-9 pellets (P1-9P) [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Figure S5. Metamorphosis assay: testing of samples obtained after treatment of P1-9 pellet (P1-9P) with digestive enzymes, heat, base and/or acid [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Figure S6. Metamorphosis assay: testing of samples obtained after treatment of lyophilized cell pellets (P1-9A) with digestive enzymes, heat, base and acid [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Figure S7. Metamorphosis assay: testing of samples obtained after organic and aqueous extraction procedures of P1-9 pellet samples (P1-9P) [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Figure S8. Metamorphosis assay: testing of supernatant obtained after threefold (3+) treatment of P1-9 pellet (P1-9A) with heat, proteinase K and acid and subsequent size-exclusion filtration (Vivaspin PES filters) [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Settlement after 24 h			
CsCL	75%		
SW	6%		
P1-9 colony	62%		
	12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
P1-9_EPS	48%	54%	53%

Metamorphosis after 24 h			
CsCL	20%		
SW	0%		
P1-9 colony	15%		
	12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
P1-9_EPS	9%	14%	0%

Settlement after 48 h			
CsCL	25%		
SW	6%		
P1-9 colony	0%		
	12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
P1-9_EPS	19%	5%	0%

Metamorphosis after 24 h			
CsCL	50%		
SW	0%		
P1-9 colony	100%		
	12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$	50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$
P1-9_EPS	40%	75%	93%

Figure S9. Metamorphosis assays of P1-9 derived enriched EPS fraction [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3].

Figure S10. Metamorphosis assays: testing organic and aqueous extracts of enzymatically or temperature-treated P1-9 pellet (P1-9P) [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

4. Structure Elucidation and Profiling of Phospholipids

Cultivation of P1-9: Cryostocks of *Pseudoalteromonas* were used to inoculate marine broth (MB) agar plates. Plates were incubated at r.t. for two days until light orange pigment production within the colonies was observed. One colony was transferred 8 mL marine broth and cultivated under shaking 180 rpm at 30 °C for two days.

A) 1 mL of preculture was used to inoculate 50 mL marine broth (250 mL culture flask) and was kept shaking at 180 rpm at 30 °C for two days. The culture was centrifuged (4000 g, r.t., 20 min) and the resulting supernatant was discarded. The cell pellet was collected and lyophilized.

B) 10 x 8 mL pre-culture was used to inoculate 10x500 mL marine broth (10 x 2 L culture flask). Cultures were incubated at 30 °C for two days (120 rpm) until the cultures produced orange pigment. The cultures were centrifuged (4000 g, r.t., 20 min) and the resulting supernatant was discarded. The cell pellet was collected and lyophilized.

Enrichment and purification of phospholipid for structure elucidation: Lyophilized P1-9 cell pellet from 1 L culture was extracted with 500 mL MeOH (ultrasonication was used to assist cell lysis). Insoluble cell debris was filtered off and the resulting filtrate collected and concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting methanolic extract was loaded on a SiOH SPE cartridge (2 g) and metabolites eluted using a step gradient of solvent mixtures (cyclohexane, EtOAc and MeOH). Metabolites were collected in eight fractions and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The metabolite content of each fraction was analyzed by UHPLC-MS and NMR and the morphogenic properties evaluated.

Table S1. Fractionation of MeOH extract of P1-9 cell pellet.

Fractions	Elution - Solvent	Morphogenic Activity
Fr. 1	Cyclohexane	-
Fr. 2	Cyclohexane/EtOAc 1:1	-
Fr. 3	EtOAc	-
Fr. 4	EtOAc/MeOH 10:1	-
Fr. 5	EtOAc/MeOH 5:1	-
Fr. 6	EtOAc/MeOH 2:1	+
Fr. 7	EtOAc/MeOH 1:1	+
Fr. 8	MeOH	+

UHPLC-MS analysis of active fractions: The concentrated fraction **8** (100% MeOH) was submitted to LC-MS analysis using the following gradient: 0–1 min, 10% B; 1–5 min, 10%–100% B; 5–7 min, 100% B; 7–7.1 min, 100%–10% B (A: dd H₂O with 0.1% FA; B: MeCN with 0.1% FA), flow rate is 0.7 mL/min.

¹H-NMR analysis of active fractions revealed typical and dominant glycerol-lipid signals within Fr. 6–7. Therefore Fr.6–Fr. 7 were submitted to semi-preparative HPLC purification using a Phenomenex Synergi Hydro-RP 250x10 mm.

Purification of Fr. 6 using the following gradient: 0–5 min, 80% B; 5–20 min, 80%–100% B; 20–30 min, 100% B; 30–32 min, 100%–80% B; 32–40 min, 80% B (A: dd H₂O with 20 mM ammonium acetate pH 9; B: MeCN, flow rate: 2.0 mL/min), resulted in a LPG/PG containing fraction (*t_R* = 25.0 min).

Purification of Fr. 7 using the following gradient: 0–5 min, 80% B; 5–20 min, 80%–100% B; 20–30 min, 100% B; 30–32 min, 100%–80% B; 32–40 min, 80% B (A: dd H₂O with 20 mM ammonium acetate pH 9; B: MeCN, flow rate of 2.0 mL/min), resulted in a LPE/PE containing fraction ($t_R = 35.0$ min).

Structural elucidation of LPG/PG and LPE/PE: Detailed NMR spectra analysis of the LPG/PG containing fraction revealed the typical fatty acid moiety of methylene groups (δ_H 2.33 ppm/ δ_C 34.9 ppm; δ_H 1.61 ppm/ δ_C 26.1 ppm; δ_H 1.37 ppm/ δ_C 30.29 ppm), terminal methyl groups (δ_H 5.35 ppm/ δ_C 130.80 ppm). The chemical shift of two sets of allylic methylene moieties (δ_H 2.04 ppm/ δ_C 28.3 ppm and δ_H 1.98 ppm/ δ_C 33.64 ppm) indicated the connected *trans*-double bond (δ_H 5.35 ppm/ δ_C 130.80 ppm) and *cis*-double bond (δ_H 5.39 ppm/ δ_C 131.55 ppm), respectively. The phosphate backbone was identified based on its substitution pattern: α -methylene groups (δ_H 3.99 ppm/ δ_C 64.73 ppm) and α -methylene group (δ_H 4.19 ppm/ δ_C 63.68 ppm) and β -methine group (δ_H 5.22 ppm/ δ_C 71.88 ppm and δ_H 3.65 ppm/ δ_C 71.12 ppm).

Based on the deshielding effect of the attached fatty chain, the appearance of PG can be deduced according to the down field shift of β -methine group (δ_H 5.22 ppm/ δ_C 71.88 ppm), comparing with the free hydroxyl group connected to β -methine group (δ_H 3.65 ppm/ δ_C 71.12 ppm) in LPG. The glycerol head group is assigned by the observation of substituted glycerol moiety with the α -methylene groups (δ_H 3.56/3.62 ppm/ δ_C 63.88 ppm and δ_H 3.86/3.91 ppm/ δ_C 67.72 ppm) and β -methine group (δ_H 3.76 ppm/ δ_C 72.58 ppm). Finally, the comparison of ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra between isolate HJ946 and commercially available PG and LPG confirmed the structural assignment.

Detailed NMR spectra analysis of fraction LPE/PE containing fraction revealed the high similarity to LPG/PG-containing fraction (**Figure S26-S27**). The presence of ethanolamine head group was deduced from the observation of the methine signals (δ_H 3.16 ppm/ δ_C 42.23 ppm and δ_H 4.04 ppm/ δ_C 63.45 ppm). Finally, comparison of ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra of LPE/PE fraction and commercially 16:1 PE and 18:1 LPE confirmed the structural assignment. Due to the overlapping chemical shifts of methine group present within the fatty chains, the position and length of the fatty acid chain was deduced from HRMS-MS² data.

In general, MS fragment ion at m/z 152.9942 indicated the phosphatidylglycerol head group. The fragment ion originated from C-2 fatty acid chain (usually the base peak) exhibited more intense than the fragment ion from C-1 fatty acid, this observation allowed us to assign the location of different fatty acids. These observations were confirmed by the fragmentation pattern from commercial LPG and PG under the same instrumentation condition.

The intensive HRMS fragmentation study has been applied to further profile the composition of LPE/PE fraction. Although LPE was not detectably by ¹H NMR, HRMS analysis clearly afforded a typical fragmentation pattern. In general, fragment ion at m/z 140.0104 indicated the phosphatidylethanolamine head group. The fragment ion originated from C-2 fatty acid chain (usually the base peak) exhibited a more intense fragment than the fragment ion from C-1 fatty acid chain, an observation which allowed us to assign the location of different fatty acids. These observations were confirmed by the fragmentation pattern from commercial LPG and PG under the same instrumentation condition.

GNPS mediated molecules networking: We then analyzed LPG/PG and LPE/PE fractions obtained from HPLC purification. Metabolomic raw data files were recorded on Thermo QExactive MS instrument and firstly converted to .mzXML by ProteoWizard, then uploaded to GNPS (Global Natural Products Social Molecular Networking) server and analyzed by Metabolomics-Snets, with the precursor ion mass tolerance as 0.02 Da and fragment ion mass tolerance as 0.02 Da as well. Advanced network options were set to: Min pairs Cos as 0.6, minimum matched

fragment ions as 10, network TopK as 6, minimum cluster size as 2 and maximum connected component size as 100. After analysis, the cytoscape data were downloaded as .zip file and finally visualized by Cytoscape.

Analysis of phospholipid content (phospholipidomics): Cryo-stock of natural isolates and commercial *Pseudoalteromonas* strains were firstly activated on marine broth agar at room temperature for two days. Then, one colony was transferred to 8 mL marine broth and incubated (180 rpm, 30 °C, 2 d). Inoculate (1 mL) was further transferred into 250 mL culture flask filled with 50-mL marine broth (180 rpm, 30 °C, 2 d). Finally, the supernatant was separated by centrifugation of the culture broth (4000 g, r.t. 20 min). The cell pellet was collected, lyophilized and extracted twice using 10 mL MeOH (assisted by ultrasonication). After centrifugation at 4000 rcf for 20 min at r.t., the supernatant was collected, pooled and dried by Speedvac finally to prepare the MeOH extracts. The crude MeOH extracts was dissolved into MeOH to a concentration of 5 mg/mL, and further diluted to 0.05 mg/mL for HPLC-HRMS analysis.

HPLC-HRMS analysis: The diluted fractions (100% MeOH) was submitted to Thermo Q-Exactive Plus analysis using the following gradient: 0–1 min, 20% B; 1–2 min, 20%–40% B; 2–25 min, 40%–92.5% B; 25–26 min, 92.5%–100% B; 26–35 min, 100% B; 35–35.1 min, 100%–20% B; 35.1–38 min, 20% B (A: dd H₂O with 20 mM ammonium formate pH 4.5; B: 50% iPrOH/50% MeCN), flow rate is 0.3 mL/min. Metabolite separation was followed by a data-dependent MS/MS analysis in both positive (MS¹) and negative (MS¹ and MS²) ionization modes. The standard lipids were analyzed under the same condition, and the retention time and MS² spectra were used for compound identification. Peak integration of identified phospholipid was performed using selective ion mode (SIM). Then, the peak area of individual phospholipids from different bacteria was compared and exhibited as the percentage of the corresponding peak area from P1-9. Using this method, the difference of phospholipid profile among different bacteria and P1-9 was investigated in order to explain the specific PG/PE profiling related to the metamorphosis effect.

Figure 11. LC-HRMS based analyses of purified lipid fraction showing (L)PE and (L)PG signals.

Figure S12. Extracted ion chromatograms of selected PG/lysoPG species for comparative phospholipidomics under negative mode, representing of [M-H]⁻: **16:0 PG** ($t_R = 26.99$ min, m/z 721.5025); **16:1 PG** ($t_R = 25.16$ min, m/z 717.4738); **16:0 16:1 PG** ($t_R = 26.14$ min, m/z 719.4895); **16:0 18:1 PG** ($t_R = 27.11$ min, m/z 747.5182); **18:1 16:1 PG** ($t_R = 26.19$ min, m/z 745.5053); **16:0 lysoPG** ($t_R = 15.92$ min, m/z 483.2729); **16:1 lysoPG** ($t_R = 13.82$ min, m/z 481.2564); **18:1 lysoPG** ($t_R = 16.43$ min, m/z 509.2887).

Figure S13. Extracted ion chromatograms of selected PE/lysoPE species for comparative phospholipidomics under negative mode, representing of $[M-H]^-$: **16:1 PE** ($t_R = 27.68$ min, m/z 686.4760); **18:0 PE** (n.d. m/z 746.5705); **16:0 16:1 PE** ($t_R = 28.65$ min, m/z 688.4921); **18:1 16:1 PE** ($t_R = 28.69$ min, m/z 714.5072); **16:0 lysoPE** ($t_R = 17.74$ min, m/z 452.2787); **16:1 lysoPE** ($t_R = 15.46$ min, m/z 450.2630); **18:0 lysoPE** ($t_R = 20.57$ min, m/z 480.3100); **18:1 lysoPE** ($t_R = 18.26$ min, m/z 478.2941).

Figure S14. Metamorphosis and settlement assays using commercial 16:0 lyso PE showed a dose dependent morphogenic activity [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

compd.	t_R (min)	m/z (M-H) ⁻	Chemical Structure	Avanti lipid: PO#
16:0 PG	26.99	721.50250		840455P (Na salt)
16:1 PG	24.72	717.47382		840457C
16:0 16:1 PG	25.74	719.48950		858122 (Na salt)
16:0 18:1 PG	27.11	747.51820		858125 (Na salt)
18:1 16:1 PG	25.92	745.50531		857123 (Na salt)
16:0 lysoPG	15.87	483.27289		856715
16:1 lysoPG	13.56	481.25635		856715
18:1 lysoPG	16.45	509.28867		846725
16:1 PE	27.68	686.47660		857123 (Na salt)
18:0 PE	n.d.	746.57050		857123 (Na salt)
16:0 16:1 PE	28.65	688.49207		810176 (ammonium salt)
18:1 16:1 PE	28.69	714.50720		810176 (ammonium salt)
16:0 lysoPE	17.74	452.27866		810110
16:1 lysoPE	15.46	450.26300		810110
18:0 lysoPE	20.57	480.31000		810110
18:1 lysoPE	18.26	478.29410		810110
16:0 PA	n.d.	647.46570		810156
16:0 18:0 PA	n.d.	675.49700		810156
18:0 PA	n.d.	703.52830		810156
16:0 lysoPA	n.d.	409.23610		810166 (ammonium salt)
16:1 lysoPA	n.d.	407.22040		810166 (ammonium salt)
18:0 lysoPA	n.d.	437.26740		810110
18:1 lysoPA	n.d.	435.25170		810110
16:0 LPE				
18:0 LPE				
18:1 LPE				
16:0 PA				830855 (Na salt)
16:0 LPA				857123 (Na salt)
18:1-12:0 NBD PE				810156
18:1-12:0 NBD PA				810176 (ammonium salt)
18:1-12:0 NBD PG				810166 (ammonium salt)
12-NBD stearate				810110

Figure S15. Structures of tested and commercially available compounds and purchase order numbers (Avanti lipid).

5. Structure Elucidation of Biopolymer

Purification of polysaccharide: Water extract (170 mg) of lyophilized P1-9 cell pellet was submitted to size exclusion chromatography by Sephadex G25 eluting by 0.1% NH_3 solution and bioassay. The most active fractions (orange band (53 mg)) were collected, lyophilized and submitted to multi-enzymatic treatments to destroy DNA, RNA and protein residues. In detail, first, lyophilized sample was suspended into 1 mL H_2O , heated to 95 °C for 1 h, then cooled on ice for 5 min. The resulting sample was then treated with DNase I (100 μL , 5 mg/mL stock solution in 0.15 M NaCl) and the mixture incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. After heating at 95 °C for 5 min, the mixture was cooled on ice for 5 min. In a third step, RNase A (100 μL , 10 mg/mL in H_2O) was added to mixture and incubated at 37 °C for 1 h. After heating at 95 °C for 5 min, the mixture was cooled on ice for 5 min. Finally, proteinase K (200 μL , 15 mg/mL in H_2O) was added into the mixture and incubated at 37 °C overnight. To denature proteins the sample was again heated at 95 °C for 5 min and then cooled on ice for 5 min. The mixture was centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min, filtered through 0.45 μm to get clear solution and applied to HPLC analysis.

Semipreparative HPLC was carried on a size exclusion chromatography by Shodex GF310HQ eluted by 20 mM NH_4OAc (pH 9) for 50 min with the flow rate of 0.5 mL/min, and coupled with fraction collector with individual fraction size of 0.5 mL to reach 50 fractions in the end. The fractions were collected, lyophilized and submitted to the metamorphosis assay. One of active fractions ($t_R = 10.0$ min) was submitted to ^1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR analysis, and a disaccharide core structure was deduced based on the diagnostic chemical shifts.

Acid hydrolysis and GC-MS analysis: To analyse the composition of the biopolymer, acid hydrolysis with HCl (1 mL, 6 N) was performed using 0.5 mg of sample. The suspension was heated to 95 °C for 10 h. After removal of acid by vacuum, the hydrolyte was submitted to TMS derivatization by adding 1 mL MSTFA and shaking for 10 min at 60 °C. The reaction mixture was directly analyzed by GC-MS coupled with ZB5 column. The authentic standard L-rhamnose and D-mannose was submitted to TMS derivatization following the same procedure and analyzed by the same method (**Figure S13**).

Figure S16. GC-MS analysis of acid hydrolyte of polysaccharide and authentic standard of L-rhamnose and D-mannose.

NMR analysis of disaccharide-containing polymer Rha-Man: Detailed analysis of the $^1\text{H-NMR}$, $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ and HSQC spectra of Rha-Man revealed that the biopolymer consisted of the repetitive incorporation of the same disaccharide unit. The disaccharide unit was deduced from the observation of 12 carbons, including one methyl group at δ_{H} 1.32 ppm/ δ_{C} 16.82 ppm, and one methylene group at δ_{H} 3.90 ppm, 3.81 ppm/ δ_{C} 60.61 ppm, and ten methine groups at δ_{H} 3.83–4.99 ppm/ δ_{C} 64.68–101.05 ppm. The free methyl group indicated the deoxy-sugar property. Analysis of COSY spectrum of **5** lead to the connection within one spin system $\delta_{\text{H}3-6}$ 1.32 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-6}$ 16.82 ppm to $\delta_{\text{H}-5}$ 4.13 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-5}$ 68.41 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-4}$ 3.75 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-4}$ 77.30 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-3}$ 4.59 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-3}$ 76.67 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-2}$ 4.42 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-2}$ 68.83 ppm, and to $\delta_{\text{H}-1}$ 4.96 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-1}$ 96.15 ppm, by the observation of COSY correlations of H₃-6 to H-5 to H-4 to H-3 to H-2 and H-1. The HMBC correlations of H₃-6 to C-4/-5, and H-4 to C-3/-5/-6, and H-3 to C-4, and H-2 to C-3/-4 and H-1 to C-3/-5 further confirmed the connection of carbon backbone from one sugar unit. The anomeric carbon was assigned at $\delta_{\text{H}-1}$ 4.96 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-1}$ 96.15 ppm based on the deshielding effect due to the glycosidic bond formation. The COSY correlations of H₂-6' to H-5' to H-4' to H-3' to H-2' to H-1' allowed to the connection of second spin system $\delta_{\text{H}2-6'}$ 3.90 ppm, 3.81 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-6'}$ 60.61 ppm to $\delta_{\text{H}-5'}$ 4.11 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-5'}$ 72.65 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-4'}$ 3.83 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-4'}$ 64.48 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-3'}$ 3.86 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-3'}$ 75.05 ppm, to $\delta_{\text{H}-2'}$ 4.21 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-2'}$ 66.49 ppm, and to $\delta_{\text{H}-1'}$ 4.99 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-1'}$ 101.05 ppm. Second anomeric carbon was assigned at $\delta_{\text{H}-1'}$ 4.99 ppm/ $\delta_{\text{C}-1'}$ 101.05 ppm based on the deshielding effect due to the glycoside bond formation. The key HMBC correlations of H-1 to C-3' and H-1' to C-4 allowed to assign the connection of disaccharide unit as $-\text{[(1'}\rightarrow\text{4)-L-Rha-(1}\rightarrow\text{3')-D-Man]}_n-$. The α -anomer of rhamnose unit was deduced by the comparison of anomeric proton reported from previous literature reports; however, the anomeric position of mannose could not be unambiguously assigned due to nonsignificant chemical differences in chemical shifts and coupling constants.⁴

Activity tests: Dose-response curve of purified polysaccharide was prepared as described in GAP9.

Table S2. NMR Data (600 MHz, D₂O, at 300 K) for $-\text{[(1'}\rightarrow\text{4)-}\alpha\text{-L-Rha-(1}\rightarrow\text{3')-D-Man]}_n-$.

position	δ_{C} , mult.	δ_{H} , mult. (<i>J</i> in Hz)	COSY	HMBC ^a
α -rhamnopyranosyl				
1	96.15, CH	4.96, s	2	3, 5, 3'
2	68.83, CH	4.42, s	1, 3	3, 4
3	76.67, CH	4.59, d, 9.85	2, 4	4
4	77.30, CH	3.75, t, 9.45	3, 5	3, 5, 6, 1'
5	68.41, CH	4.13, m	4, 6	
6	16.82, CH ₃	1.32, d, 5.41	5	4, 5
mannopyranosyl				
1'	101.15, CH	4.99, s	2'	4, 2', 3', 5'
2'	66.49, CH	4.21, s	1', 3'	3', 4'
3'	75.05, CH	3.86, m	2'	1, 4'
4'	64.48, CH	3.83, m	5'	3, 5, 6
5'	72.65, CH	4.11, m	4', 6a'	
6'	60.61, CH ₂	3.90, m	5'	
		3.81, m		

Figure S17. Metamorphosis and settlement assays of the isolated biopolymer Rha-Man showed a dose-dependent morphogenic activity; A) metamorphosis in % after 24 h; B) metamorphosis in % after 48 h [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3, error bars indicate ± 0.5 standard deviation].

Compound	Monomer	Glycosidic linkage	Size
dextran 20	α -D-glucose	α -1,6 linear	≈ 20 kD
dextran 70	α -D-glucose	α -1,6 linear	≈ 70 kD
dextran 150	α -D-glucose	α -1,6 linear	≈ 150 kD
curdlan	β -D-glucose	β -1,3 linear	≈ 50 -200 kD
β -1,3-glucan	β -D-glucose	β -1,3 linear	≈ 500 kD
laminarin	β -D-glucose	β -1,3 linear	≈ 13 kD
xanthan	β -D-glucose	β -1,4 linear	≈ 2000 kD
	β -D-mannose	β -1,3 branching	
hyaluronic acid	β -D-glucuronic acid	β -1,3 linear	≈ 150 -180 kD
	β -N-acetylglucosamine		
alginate	α -L-glucuronic acid	α -1,4 and β -1,4 linear	20-40 kD
	β -D-mannuronic acid		
heparin	glucosamine	β -1,4 and α -1,4 linear	≈ 20 kD
	β -D-uronic acid		

Figure S18. Structures and composition of tested bacterial polysaccharides.

6. Fluorescence Microscopy Imaging

The nitrobenzoxadiazole (NBD)-labeled phospholipids (Avanti Polar Lipids, Alabama, USA) were dissolved into MeOH to give a 1 mg/mL stock solution. For testing, 25 µg of each lipid was added per well which contained glass slides at the bottom for larvae attachment. Samples were dried under sterile laminar flow. Then, 20-30 competent larvae were added and the well filled up with sterile artificial sea water to reach 2 mL in total. The plates were placed in dark at 20 °C. Sterile artificial sea water was used as negative control and the 120 mM CsCl in ASW was used as positive control. After 5, 24 and 48 h glass slides were transferred to an object slide and larvae development and fluorescence detection was monitored on a Zeiss Axio Imager M1 fluorescence microscope.

7. Scanning Electron microscopy (SEM) and cryo-Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

Isolated OMV/minicell solution (20 µl) were placed for 1 min onto hydrophilic, Formvar®/carbon-filmed copper grids (Quantifoil Micro Tools GmbH, Germany), washed twice on drops of distilled water, and stained on a drop of 2 % uranyl acetate in distilled water. Samples were imaged in a Zeiss EM902A electron microscope (Carl Zeiss AG, Germany) operated at 80 kV accelerating voltage. Images were acquired with a 1k × 1k FastScan-F114 CCD-camera (TVIPS GmbH, Germany).

Morphology of OMV was additionally studied by cryo-TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy). A drop of OMV solution (2 µl) was placed on a R3.5/1 holey carbon filmed copper grid (Quantifoil Micro Tools GmbH, Germany). The sample was rapidly plunge-frozen in liquid ethane at –180°C. The frozen grid was transferred into a liquid nitrogen cooled Gatan 626-DH cryo-holder (Gatan Inc., USA) and inserted into a Philips CM 120 cryo-TEM (Philips, Netherlands) operated at 120 kV accelerating voltage. Images were captured using a CCD-camera type s.o.

The morphology of cells was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The bacteria were fixed with glutaraldehyde (2.5%, v/v) for 1h at RT while sedimenting on poly-L-lysine coated coverslips. After two washings in cacodylate buffer (100 mM, Ph 7.2) cells were dehydrated by increasing concentrations of ethanol, followed by critical point drying in a Leica EM CPD300 Automated Critical Point Dryer (Leica, Germany). Then, the cover slips were mounted on aluminum sample holders (stubs) and gold sputter coated (layer thickness 20 nm) in a BAL-TEC SCD 005 Sputter Coater (BAL-TEC, Liechtenstein). Images were acquired with a Zeiss (LEO) 1530 Gemini field emission scanning electron microscope (Zeiss AG, Germany) at 4 kV acceleration voltage and a working distance of 3-4 mm using an Inlense secondary electron detector.

8. Assay Data and Spectra

Figure S19. ¹H NMR spectrum of commercial and isolated EPS fraction (D₂O, 600 MHz, 300 K). Curdlan and β-1,3-glucan were not soluble in D₂O.

Figure S20. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of polysaccharide (D₂O, 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S21. $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectrum of polysaccharide (D₂O, 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S22. DEPT 135 spectrum of polysaccharide (D_2O , 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S23. $^1\text{H-}^1\text{H}$ COSY spectrum of polysaccharide (D_2O , 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S24. $^1\text{H-}^{13}\text{C}$ HSQC spectrum of polysaccharide (D_2O , 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S25. $^1\text{H-}^{13}\text{C}$ HMBC spectrum of polysaccharide (D_2O , 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S26. ^1H NMR spectra comparison of isolated lipids and commercial standards.

Figure S27. ^{13}C NMR spectra comparison of isolated lipids and commercial standards.

Figure S28. ^1H NMR spectrum of LPG/PG fraction (CD_3OD , 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S29. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of LPG/PG fraction (CD_3OD , 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S30. ¹H NMR spectrum of LPE/PE fraction (CD₃OD/CHCl₃, 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S31. ¹³C NMR spectrum of LPE/PE fraction (CD₃OD/CHCl₃, 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S32. ¹H NMR spectrum of 16:0/18:1 PG (CD₃OD, 500 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S33. ¹³C NMR spectrum of 16:0/18:1 PG (CD₃OD, 125 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S34. ¹H NMR spectrum of 18:1 LPG (CD₃OD, 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S35. ¹³C NMR spectrum of 18:1 LPG (CD₃OD, 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S36. ^1H NMR spectrum of 16:1 PE (CD_3OD , 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S37. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 16:1 PE (CD_3OD , 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S38. ^1H NMR spectrum of 18:1 LPE ($\text{CD}_3\text{OD}/\text{CDCl}_3$, 600 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S39. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 18:1 LPE ($\text{CD}_3\text{OD}/\text{CDCl}_3$, 150 MHz, 300 K).

Figure S40. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:0 LPG.

Figure S41. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:1 LPG.

Figure S42. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 18:1 LPG.

Figure S43. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:0/16:1 PG.

Figure S44. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:1/18:1 PG.

Figure S45. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:0 LPE.

Figure S46. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:1 LPE.

Figure S47. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 18:0 LPE.

Figure S48. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 18:1 LPE.

Figure S49. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:0/16:1 PE.

Figure S50. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of 16:1/18:1 PE.

Figure S51. HRMS analysis of metabolites known to be produced by *Pseudoaltermonas* species: (a, b), EIC of 2,3,4-tribromopyrrole and tetrabromopyrrole from MeOH extract of *Pseudoaltermonas* sp. PS5 at m/z 299.76727 and m/z 377.67816 under negative mode; (c) extract ion chromatogram (EIC) of violacein from MeOH extract of *Pseudoaltermonas luteoviolacea* at m/z 342.08884 under negative mode.

Figure S52. ESI-HRMS spectrum of 2,3,4-tribromopyrrole.

Figure S53. ESI-HRMS spectrum of tetrabromopyrrole.

Figure S54. ESI-HRMS spectrum of violacein.

Figure S55. ESI-HRMS/MS spectrum of violacein.

Table S3. Fluorescence labeling images of larvae treated with 12-NBD stearate, 18:1-12:0-NBD PE, 18:1-12:0-NBD PG and 18:1-12:0 NBD PA (fluorescence imaging (20x50 ms) with emission wavelength at 527 nm) [negative control: ASW; positive control: 6 mM CsCl; n = 3]

5 h	24 h	48 h	Compound
	12-NBD stearate		
	12-NBD stearate		
	18:1-12:0 NBD PE		
	18:1-12:0 NBD PE		
	18:1-12:0 NBD PG		
	18:1-12:0 NBD PG		

9. References

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